

A STUDY ON DECISION-MAKING SKILLS OF SECONDARY TEACHER EDUCATION STUDENTS

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Abstract:

Teachers are responsible for guiding the students to learn by providing clear directions and explanations in order to educate the future generation. In the present study, the investigator has attempted to study the decision-making skills of secondary teacher education students. The sample consisted of 900 secondary teacher education students, who were studying B.Ed. degree in colleges of education in Tirunelveli, Kanyakumari and Thoothukudi districts and the investigator adapted survey method. The findings of the study were, i) No significant difference was found between male and female students in their decision-making skills and its dimensions and ii) significant difference was found between rural and urban area secondary teacher education students in their decision-making skills and its dimensions.

Introduction:

Decision-making is one of the most important functions of teachers. Decision-making means 'choosing one alternative from many available options'. It is a tough task and the ability to tackle depends on one's mental ability. In the words of Terry (2001) decision-making is "the selection based on some criteria of one behavior alternative from two or more possible alternatives". In the words of Moore (2001), "Decision-making is a blend of thinking, deciding and acting". According to Encyclopedia of Social Sciences, "Decision-making is a social process that selects a problem for decision (i.e., choice) and produces a limited number of alternatives, from among which a particular alternative is selected for implementation and execution.

Significance of the Study:

The present generation of students is emotionally troubled more than the previous and the students are growing more lonely and depressed, more angry and unruly, more nervous and prone to worry, more impulsive and aggressive. Decision making can be regarded as the mental process (cognitive process) resulting in the selection of a course of action among several alternatives. Every decision-making process produces a final choice. The output can be an action or an opinion of choice. Decision-making is a major responsibility of all administrators. It is the process by which decisions are not only arrived but also implemented. The process of decision-making involves a cycle of steps, starting with the definition of the problem, selecting alternatives for action and implementing. Information monitoring and reporting must be built in the action cycle for continuous evaluation. The secondary teacher education students are acquiring skills for classroom management and guidance. They have to make right decisions in the right time for the right situations. Decision-making involves rational thinking and high self-esteem. In this study, the investigator attempts to identify the decision-making skills of the secondary teacher education students.

Objectives:

- ✓ To find out the level of decision-making skills of secondary teacher education students.
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant difference between male and female secondary teacher education students in their decision-making skills.
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant difference between rural and urban secondary teacher education students of in their decision-making skills.

Hypotheses:

H₀1: There is no significant difference between male and female secondary teacher education students in their decision-making skills.

H₀2: There is no significant difference between rural and urban secondary teacher education students in their decision-making skills.

Methods Used: In the present study the investigator has adopted the survey method.

Tools Used: Decision-making Skill Inventory developed and validated by the investigator.

Statistical Techniques Used: Percentage analysis and 't' test were used in this study.

Analysis of Data:

Table 1: Level of Decision-Making Skills of Secondary Teacher Education Students

0	Low		Moderate		High	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
1. Holistic	148	16.4	565	62.8	187	20.8
2. Control	166	18.5	543	60.3	191	21.2

3. Social residence	199	22.1	518	57.6	183	20.3
4. Hesitancy	220	24.5	461	51.2	219	24.3
5. Optimizing	215	23.9	493	54.8	192	21.3
6. Principal based	204	22.7	485	53.9	211	23.4
7. Instinctiveness	172	19.1	520	57.8	208	23.1
Decision-making skills in Total	212	23.5	465	51.7	223	24.8

It is inferred from the above table that 23.5% of the students have low, 51.7% of them have moderate and 24.8% of them have high level of decision-making skills in total.

Table 2: Difference between male and female secondary teacher education students in their decision-making skills

Dimensions	Gender	N	Mean	S.D	Calculated 't' value	Remarks at 5% level
1. Holistic	Male	203	21.62	4.897	1.40	NS
	Female	697	21.11	4.483		
2. Control	Male	203	18.77	3.821	1.08	NS
	Female	697	18.46	3.544		
3. Social resistance	Male	203	21.54	4.544	1.24	NS
	Female	697	21.14	3.875		
4. Hesitancy	Male	203	21.38	3.916	1.84	NS
	Female	697	20.84	3.560		
5. Optimizing	Male	203	21.48	4.295	1.45	NS
	Female	697	21.01	3.971		
6. Principle based	Male	203	27.27	5.991	1.40	NS
	Female	697	26.65	5.397		
7. Instinctiveness	Male	203	24.83	4.841	0.75	NS
	Female	697	24.54	4.843		
Decision-making skills in Total	Male	203	156.88	26.425	1.63	NS
	Female	697	153.74	23.327		

(The table value of 't' is 1.96, NS - Not Significant)

It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference between male and female students in their decision-making skills.

Table 3: Difference between rural and urban secondary teacher education students in their decision-making skills

Dimensions	Locality of Residence	N	Mean	S.D	Calculated 't' value	Remarks at 5% level
1. Holistic	Rural	536	20.98	4.782	1.98	S
	Urban	364	21.58	4.250		
2. Control	Rural	536	18.21	3.687	3.24	S
	Urban	364	19.00	3.442		
3. Social resistance	Rural	536	20.90	3.923	2.97	S
	Urban	364	21.71	4.155		
4. Hesitancy	Rural	536	20.59	3.606	3.78	S
	Urban	364	21.52	3.643		
5. Optimizing	Rural	536	20.70	4.097	3.74	S
	Urban	364	21.72	3.902		
6. Principle based	Rural	536	26.57	5.664	2.44	S
	Urban	364	27.11	5.340		
7. Instinctiveness	Rural	536	24.19	4.842	3.14	S
	Urban	364	25.21	4.782		
Decision-making skills	Rural	536	152.13	24.161	3.52	S
	Urban	364	157.86	23.584		

(The table value of 't' is 1.96, S - Significant)

It is inferred from the above table that there is significant difference between rural and urban students in their holistic, control, social resistance, hesitancy, optimizing, principle based, instinctiveness and decision-making skills. Urban students are better in their decision-making skills.

Findings:

- ✓ 23.5% of the students have low, 51.7% of them have moderate and 24.8% of them have high level of decision-making skills.

- ✓ There is no significant difference between male and female students in their decision-making skills.
- ✓ There is significant difference between rural and urban students in their holistic, control, social resistance, hesitancy, optimizing, principle based, instinctiveness and decision-making skills. Urban students are better in their decision-making skills.

Recommendations:

- ✓ The teacher educators should render necessary strategies for developing more social resistance among secondary teacher education students. For rural area secondary education students those teacher educators should provide a constructive climate or environment to have extra life experience and more chances to expose the realities of life in an urban setup.
- ✓ Teacher educator should encourage the students to participate in curricular and co-curricular activities to develop social skills among the secondary teacher education students.

Conclusion:

Decision-making appears to be engaged in all aspects of human interaction. In the present scenario, number of challenges is ahead of secondary teacher education students and they are in a position to overcome those problems with mental stability. According to psychologists' a person who can behave properly and deal with people have good decision-making skills. To perform well and to be successful in one's profession, the ability to make intelligent decisions using their higher order thinking skill is really mandatory. The secondary teacher education students have to deal with their responsibility both in their family and in their profession. They would have to tackle the depressing moments, negative experience and practical difficulties in working conditions. So the investigation is made on the abilities of secondary teacher education students to think rationally and to make decisions systematically by adopting the concepts of decision-making.

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